

Unveiling Structural, Electronic, Mechanical and Optical Properties of LiTaO_3 for Potential Optoelectronic Applications by Density Functional Theory

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Abstract:

Applying density functional theory different physical aspects of LiTaO_3 perovskite including structural, electronic, mechanical and optical properties have been analyzed by Generalized Gradient Approximation with PBE and RPBE approaches. LiTaO_3 crystal possesses indirect bandgap values of 2.24 and 2.27 eV respectively in PBE and RPBE techniques. Through density of states variety of nature and contribution of atomic orbital in LiTaO_3 crystal were studied. The analysis of Mulliken population charge revealed important details regarding the bonding features of LiTaO_3 crystal. The verification of mechanical stability was conducted through the application of the Born stability criterion, while Poisson's ratio and Pugh's ratio were analysed to evaluate ductile strength and elastic anisotropy. The LiTaO_3 crystal exhibits notable mechanical and thermal stability, as well as ductile characteristics and elastic anisotropy. The optical properties were meticulously assessed with an emphasis on energy and wavelength, and both methods validated that LiTaO_3 crystal exhibits the potentiality for strong contender in optoelectronics and photocatalytic applications.

Keywords: Electronic structure, DOS, PDOS, Mechanical, Optical, Optoelectronic.

Introduction

Natural gas, gasoline, and biofuels are mostly utilized for generating electricity, supplying heat, and powering transportation systems [1-2]. Nevertheless, if they are kept in use, they will continue to harm the environment and drain precious resources. Scholars are working tirelessly to find new energy sources and improve upon existing ones by expanding the frontiers of material science and discovering innovative materials [3-5]. To address the increasing global energy demand, it is crucial to do this study continuously in order to find sustainable solutions. "A" stands for alkaline earth metals like Li, Cs, Ca, Sr etc, "B" for transition or rare-earth metals like Ti, Mn, Fe, V, Ta, Nb; and "O" for the oxide ion; the ABO_3 formula is commonly used to describe oxide-perovskites. Perovskite materials are very compatible with current economic infrastructures and are inexpensive [6-7]. Computational methods have recently advanced to the point that many more material properties, including electrical, magnetic, and mechanical ones, may be evaluated. The correctness of these computational approaches is supported by the remarkable correlation between their results and experimental data [8]. Theoretical investigations of several semiconductors, such as KTaO_3 , KNbO_3 ,

CsTaO₃, etc., have focused heavily on these materials because of their high photocatalytic activity and huge surface areas [9–11]. Although many are interested in the potential uses of Ta and its derivatives, LiTaO₃ has not received much attention in this field. There must be a comprehensive scientific evaluation of LiTaO₃ before its technical implementation [12]. Theoretical investigations of these aspects using first-principles computation have also shown to be highly effective [13–14]. So far, the physical properties of LiTaO₃ have received minimal attention from scientists. We dug further into LiTaO₃ crystal and collected further data on its physical properties in an effort to address this knowledge gap. We addressed several physical properties of the LiTaO₃ crystal adopting Perdew Burke Ernzerhof (PBE) and Revised Perdew Burke Ernzerhof (RPBE). Future experimental investigations should be considerably aided by our study, which will lead to improved understanding of this material for future world.

Computational details

To accomplish very accurate computations, this work used $6 \times 6 \times 6$ k-point mesh and pseudopotentials with a 500 eV cutoff energy [15]. Achieving overall energy convergence to within 0.2000×10^{-4} eV/atom was the result of structural optimization performed using the BFGS method. Furthermore, an ionic force of 0.5000×10^{-1} eV/Å was recorded, an ionic displacement of 0.2000×10^{-2} Å, and a stress component of 0.1000 GPa achieved.

Results and discussion

Structural analysis

Starting with a lattice parameter of 3.89 Å and angles $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$, the structural refinement of LiTaO₃ crystals was initiated. In terms of space group Pm3̄m, the optimized LiTaO₃ crystal takes on a cubic form [221]. The point group Pm3m and the Hall symbol -P 423, which belong to the crystal, provide further crystallographic details. The ideal LiTaO₃ combinations are summarized in Table 1 and Figure 1 shows the crystal structure of the cubical LiTaO₃.

Figure 1 Crystal structure of LiTaO₃

Table 1 Final energy, cell volume and lattice parameter of LiTaO₃ crystal

Material Name	Final Energy (eV)	Cell volume (Å ³)	Lattice constant a=b=c (Å)	Approaches
LiTaO ₃	- 46.405426800	6.854298	3.8452192	PBE
	- 47.646209197	57.180456	3.852558	RPBE

Electronic band structure

According to band structure, specifically their band gap energy, materials are categorized as insulators, semiconductors, or metals [16–17]. From Figures 2 (a) and 2 (b), LiTaO₃ crystal

is found to be a semiconductor by calculating its narrow indirect band gap utilizing techniques such as PBE and RPBE methods respectively while K points occurs from X-R-M-Γ-R and summarized in Table 2.

Bandgap Value (eV)	Techniques Name
2.24	PBE
2.27	RPBE

Table 2 Bandgap values of LiTaO₃ crystal

Figure 2 Band structure of LiTaO₃ by (a) PBE, (b) RPBE methods respectively

The distribution of energy level in a material and separation of occupied states from unoccupied is clarify using density of states (DOS) plot [18-19]. The semiconductor nature is improved by the variation of different energy band by illustrating DOS and PDOS of LiTaO₃ in Figure 3 (a, b) for both methods, where maximum density of states in valence and conduction band reaches 5.0 and 4.0 electrons/eV.

The PDOS analysis presented in Figure 4 (a, b) reveals that within the valence band, the Li atom little contributed via the s orbital, while the Ta atom contributes through the s, p and d orbitals. Finally, the O atom primarily contributes through the s, p orbital [20]. The primary contributions in the conduction band stem from the Li-s, Ta-d, and O-p orbitals. The major peak in valence band composed by Ta-s/p/d and and O-s/p orbitals. The notable peak in conduction band arises due to combined effect of Li-s, Ta-p/d and O-p orbitals.

Figure 4 Different states of Li, Ta and O atom.

Mechanical Properties

For mechanical stability, every cubic perovskite must fill-up the stability criteria of Born, as outlined in [22]: $C_{11} > 0$, $C_{44} > 0$, $C_{11} - C_{12} > 0$, and $C_{11} + 2C_{12} > 0$.

The mechanical properties of LiTaO₃, as assessed through PBE and RPBE methods, are presented in Table 3, confirming its stability under specific conditions.

The response of the material to stress-induced volume variations can be analyzed through the calculation of the Cauchy pressure, defined as

$C_{12} - C_{44}$. A positive Cauchy pressure signifies ductility and metallic bonding, while a negative Cauchy pressure indicates brittleness and the existence of directed bonding, including covalent or partly ionic contacts. The negative estimated value of LiTaO₃ indicates strong directional bonding, such as covalent or partially ionic interactions, and implies a brittle nature.

Additionally, Pugh's ratio B/G , a reliable indicator of mechanical pliability or brittleness, was used to evaluate the ductile or brittle behavior of the material. An indicative ratio of $B/G > 1.75$ suggests ductile behavior according

to this standard, whereas $B/G < 1.75$ implies brittleness. The computed value of Pugh for LiTaO_3 is 1.40, which is below the critical value, suggesting that the material exhibits brittle mechanical behavior. The consistency of Pugh's ratio and Cauchy pressure lends strong support to these findings. High bulk modulus (B) values signify strong elasticity, incompressibility, and stiffness, which are characteristic of LiTaO_3 and elevated Young's modulus of LiTaO_3 denotes its stiffness, rigidity, and resistance to deformation under tensile or compressive stress, reflecting robust mechanical stability. The shear modulus (G) demonstrates a significant resistance to shear deformation, thereby ensuring the stability of structures [23]. Materials with a Poisson's ratio below 0.5 often possess robust atomic or molecule bonding, since they exhibit resistance

to deformation while still experiencing lateral contraction or expansion under tensile or compressive forces, with diminishing strength as the ratio approaches 0.5. The atomic and molecular interactions of LiTaO_3 are robust, as indicated by the assessed Poisson's ratios of 0.21 and 0.20 in both approaches. The strong rigidity and mechanical stability of the cubic LiTaO_3 crystal evidenced by the moderate anisotropy values of 0.88 and 0.90 obtained through both methods for the universal anisotropy index [24].

Table 3 Values of elastic constants and other parameter of LiTaO_3 crystal.

Techniques Name	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	$C_{12}-C_{44}$	B	Y	G	B/G	ν	A
PBE	506.72	41.59	75.39	- 33.80	196.63	336.03	138.26	1.42	0.21	0.88
RPBE	495.29	48.02	96.11	-48.09	197.11	353.43	147.12	1.33	0.20	0.90

Optical properties:

All computational approaches used a 0.1 eV Gaussian smearing to examine the optical characteristics of LiTaO_3 crystal. Reflection measurements presented in Figure 5 (a, b) demonstrate a notable increase from 1.0 eV to 23 eV, with all methods indicating peak reflectivity only around 0.78 eV in both PBE

and RBE approaches. The energy loss function, an essential parameter for enhancing energy efficiency in optoelectronics, is illustrated in Figure 5 (c, d). Results indicate that the LiTaO_3 crystal exhibits lower energy loss in both methods, with the PBE method yielding lower values than the RPBE method.

Figure 5 (a, b) Optical reflectivity, (c, d) Loss function

Optical conductivity reflects a material's ability to transmit visible light, with the real component indicating conductivity and the imaginary component representing energy dissipation [31]. As shown in Figure 6 (a, b), real component surpasses the imaginary component between 2.5 and 11.0 eV, then gradually decreases by 25 eV. Conversely, the imaginary component dominates from 10.0 to

25.0 eV, highlighting variations in energy absorption and conductivity.

Dielectric functions are essential for comprehending optical behavior and for the design of tailored blends [32]. Figure 6 (c, d) illustrates that the real part of LiTaO_3 predominates over the imaginary part from 0 to 5.0 eV, subsequently decreasing up to 25.0 eV. In the energy range of 5.0 to 25.0 eV, the imaginary component surpasses the real component, signifying considerable absorption in the presence of an electric field.

Figure 6 (a, b) Conductivity and (c, d) Dielectric function

The inspection of the refractive index in Figure 7 (a, b) demonstrates an inverse relationship between the real and imaginary components in both techniques [33]. Between 0 and 5 eV, the real component of the refractive index surpasses the imaginary component, signifying predominant refractive characteristics and little

absorption. In the 5 to 25 eV region, the imaginary component exceeds the real portion, indicating significant absorption. This result indicates that LiTaO₃ has increased optical absorption in the higher energy spectrum, which substantially affects its optical characteristics and renders it appropriate for applications like optical filters and protective coatings.

Figure 7 (a, b) Refractive index of LiTaO₃ crystal

The absorption spectra of LiTaO_3 depicted in Figure 8(a, b), exhibit a uniform trend ranging from 0 to 25 eV, as established through the application of the PBE and RPBE methodologies. In the visible spectrum (1.78–4.14 eV or 300–700 nm), the material exhibits notable absorption, with a peak observed at 3.76 eV across all utilized techniques [34-35].

Figure 8. Optical absorption (a, b) against energy (eV) and (c, d) wavelength (nm)

Furthermore, the absorption coefficient curves of LiTaO_3 against wavelength are presented in Figures 8 (c, d) respectively. Throughout the visible spectrum (300 to 700 nm), the data illustrates distinct absorption peaks. The peak absorption for both methods observed near 325 nm. The wavelengths identified align with the areas where LiTaO_3 demonstrates maximum light absorption, underscoring its significant absorption characteristics at these particular wavelengths. Furthermore, the absorption characteristics observed in the visible spectrum demonstrate that LiTaO_3 shows considerable sensitivity to visible light, implying its possible

Additionally, the ultraviolet (UV) spectrum displays a variety of absorption peaks, with the most significant peak identified at 11.0 eV. This action emphasizes the exceptional and extensive optical absorption properties of LiTaO_3 by showcasing its effectiveness in absorbing light across the visible and ultraviolet spectrums [36].

applications in fields such as optoelectronics and photocatalysis, where accurate light control and detection are essential [37].

Conclusion:

Exploring structural, electrical, elastic, and optical phenomena of cubic LiTaO_3 crystals conducted by first principle simulations. The band gap energies (E_g) estimated using the PBE, RPBE, functional successively reveal an indirect bandgap with values of 2.24 eV, 2.27 eV. Mulliken population study was conducted to better grasp the bonding characteristics of LiTaO_3 . The exceptional mechanical stability of the material, together with its great ductility elastic anisotropies of LiTaO_3 are visualized and discussed, indicating that it can easily

resist mechanical stress. Furthermore, the high value of Young's and Shear modulus of this crystal are anticipated. LiTaO_3 crystals may serve as outstanding candidates for advancing optoelectronic and photocatalytic applications in the future for suitable bandgap and absorption capabilities.

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors hereby declare there is no conflict of interest.

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